

Molecular Identification of Mycobacterium Tuberculosis Complex in Suspected Bovine Lung Tissue Samples from Plateau, Borno and Taraba States, Nigeria

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Abstract

Globally and in Nigeria, a zoonotic bacterial disease commonly seen in cattle is bovine tuberculosis (bTB), usually chronic and caused by the members of Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex (MTBC), primarily *Mycobacterium bovis* and *Mycobacterium caprae*, and occasionally *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Despite its public health relevance, rapid identification of specific MTBC species responsible for bTB in cattle across Nigeria remains limited. This study aimed to determine the specific MTBC species causing bTB and assess their zoonotic implications among high-risk groups in selected Nigerian states. Surveillance and diagnostic lung tissue samples were collected from subclinical cattle in abattoirs located in Jos (Plateau State), Maiduguri (Borno State) and Jalingo (Taraba State), Nigeria. A total of 120 lung tissues were processed between April and July 2024 using polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for MTBC detection. Out of the 120 samples analyzed, 52% tested positive for MTBC. Among the positive cases, 69% were from female cattle and 31% from males, with *M. bovis* specifically detected in 17% of the total samples. These results indicate ongoing circulation of MTBC, particularly *M. bovis* within the cattle population. This study confirms the continued presence and transmission of MTBC species, especially *M. bovis*, in cattle across the study locations, underscoring their zoonotic potential. Strengthening integrated, rapid and routine surveillance systems is recommended to enhance early detection, control transmission, and protect both animal and human health.

Keywords: Abattoir, Bovine tuberculosis, Lungs, *M. bovis*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC), Public Health

1.1 Introduction

Surpassing HIV/AIDS, Tuberculosis (TB) remains the leading cause of death from a single infectious agent. Geographically, the burden of TB is highest in Asia and Africa and almost 80% of TB cases among people living with HIV reside in Africa [1,2]. Furthermore, about one-quarter of the global population are said to harbour latent TB infection

(LTBI), representing a substantial reservoir for future transmission [3]. Tuberculosis is distinctively higher in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, even though it is a global health concern [4]. Infections are predominantly higher in Nigeria and South Africa, driven by both socioeconomic factors and coexisting health challenges such as HIV [5,6].

One of the forms of TB with significant health consequences is bovine tuberculosis (bTB) [7]. bTB is a chronic, zoonotic infectious disease which primarily affects cattle but can also infect other domesticated and wild animals, as well as humans, posing significant public health and economic challenges [7]. The disease is caused by members of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC), notably *M. bovis* and *M. caprae*, with occasional infections by *M. tuberculosis* [7]. The World Health Organization classified zoonotic tuberculosis, which is *M. bovis* infection in humans as a neglected tropical disease [8]. It is estimated that bTB accounts for over 1% of global TB cases, particularly in regions where close contact between humans and livestock is common [9]. Infection with *M. bovis* is of particular concern due to its ability to infect a wide range of hosts and its intrinsic resistance to pyrazinamide, a first-line anti-tuberculosis drug, thereby complicating treatment in human [10]. The persistence of bTB not only threatens animal health and agricultural productivity but also poses a significant risk to public health, especially in settings with weak veterinary infrastructure, limited surveillance, and high rates of human-animal interaction [11].

In Most countries, the transmission of zoonotic TB to humans has predominantly been associated with the consumption of contaminated animal products, particularly unpasteurized dairy products [12]. Direct transmission through animal-to-human or human-to-human contact is less commonly reported [13,14]. In Nigeria, the disease is said to be endemic, largely due to inadequate surveillance, limited diagnostic capacity, and weak control measures, resulting in economic losses in the livestock sector [15]. In addition, poor meat inspection at slaughter, inadequate awareness of zoonotic TB and unhygienic practices at the abattoir are potential risk factors for the disease in humans [16].

Conventional diagnostic methods, including culture and microscopy, are dependable but require extended incubation times, typically four to eight weeks, which can significantly delay timely intervention [17]. In contrast, molecular diagnostic tools such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR) have emerged as rapid and specific alternatives, capable of distinguishing *M. bovis* from other MTBC species, thereby enhancing disease surveillance and control efforts [18]. The classical laboratory diagnosis also requires containment facility that is

not readily available hence molecular diagnostic in Biosafety Level 2 (BSL2) after processing samples in BSL3 laboratory offers safe and rapid turnaround diagnostic option for MTBC.

In Nigeria, access to confirmatory testing remains limited despite the advantages of molecular diagnostics [19], with only a few specialized laboratories like the National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI), Vom, equipped to perform definitive TB diagnoses under strict public health protocols. This diagnostic gap, particularly in high-risk settings such as abattoirs, underscores the need for integrated approaches to detect and control bTB. This study was therefore conducted in selected abattoirs in Plateau, Borno and Taraba States in Nigeria, to identify the specific MTBC species responsible for bovine tuberculosis and assess the potential zoonotic transmission risks among occupationally exposed individuals. The findings aim to inform and strengthen current control strategies in line with the One Health framework, targeting both animal and human health outcomes.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Location

This study was carried out in Jos main abattoir in Jos metropolis of Plateau State, Maiduguri main abattoir in Borno State, and Jalingo main abattoir, Taraba state, Nigeria. This study focused on Plateau, Borno, and Taraba states because they represent major livestock production and trade corridors in Nigeria, where cattle movement and human-animal interactions are intensive. Jos, in Plateau State with latitude $\sim 9.93^\circ$ N and longitude $\sim 8.89^\circ$ E, is a key agricultural hub and supplies cattle and dairy products across the country. Maiduguri, the capital of Borno State with latitude $\sim 11.85^\circ$ N and longitude $\sim 13.16^\circ$ E, lies within the Sudano-Sahelian zone and serves as a major livestock market and transit point due to its proximity to the borders with Cameroon, Chad, and Niger [20], (Fig.1). Jalingo, in Taraba State with latitude $\sim 8.89^\circ$ N and longitude $\sim 11.36^\circ$ E, is an administrative and economic centre located within the Benue River Basin [21] (Fig.1), supporting extensive cattle rearing and cross-state trade.

These areas were chosen because their high levels of livestock production, cross-border animal movement, and human-cattle contact create conditions favourable for the transmission and persistence of bovine tuberculosis. Targeting these

regions therefore provides valuable insights into the molecular epidemiology of *Mycobacterium*

tuberculosis complex in Nigerian cattle populations.

Fig. 1. Map of Nigeria with locations of sample collection

2.2 Study design

A cross-sectional study design was used to conduct this study to identify MTBC in suspected bovine lung tissue samples from selected states in Nigeria.

2.3 Population of the study

The population of study were the cattle slaughtered at the period the study was carried out in the three slaughter facilities mentioned.

2.5 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

All sub-clinical and apparently healthy cattle brought in for slaughter in the mentioned slaughter facilities at the period of study were included. While those excluded are cattle in the facilities that were yet to be slaughtered at the time the study was going on.

2.4 Sample Size Determination

The sample size for the study was determined using the formula by Thrusfield [22]:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \times p \times (1-p)}{d^2}$$

Where:

n= required sample size

Z = Z-score for a 95% confidence level (1.96)

P = expected prevalence of bovine tuberculosis (bTB) in Nigeria

d = desired absolute precision (margin of error, commonly set at 0.05 or 5%)

The expected prevalence (P) was taken as 8.3% (P=0.083) [23], while d was considered as 0.05

Therefore,

$$n = \frac{(1.96^2) \times 0.083 \times (1-0.083)}{0.05^2}$$

$$n = \frac{(3.8416 \times 0.083 \times 0.917)}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 0.292 / 0.0025$$

n=116.8 samples. However, 120 samples were collected to increase precision.

2.6 Sampling Technique

The probability sampling technique was used for this study.

2.7 Sample collection

A total of 120 bovine lung tissue samples with no characteristic tuberculous lesion with subclinical signs were collected from slaughterhouses in Jos, Maiduguri, and Jalingo over six months, from March 2024 to August 2024. The sample distribution across the three sample locations was as follows; at the Jos main abattoir in Plateau State: 100 lung samples were collected (70 from female cattle and 30 from male cattle), at the Maiduguri main abattoir in Borno State, 11 lung samples were collected (8 from female cattle and 3 from male cattle), and Jalingo main abattoir in Taraba State, 9 lung tissue samples were collected, (7 from female cattle and 2 from male cattle). The procedure of collection was adopted from [24]. The sample size was not uniform across the locations sampled due to the constraint of time during the study. Post mortem examination was performed on the animals before sampling (Plate 1) following the standard procedure

Plate 1: Physical examination of cows antemortem

2.8 Breeds and Sex Identification

The breeds of cattle sampled were white Fulani and red Bororo breed which were the cattle predominantly slaughtered and reared in these locations. While the sex identification was based on information given to us in these slaughter facilities by the butchers themselves.

2.9 Post-Mortem Examination

Post-mortem examination was done when the cattle is slaughtered and the lungs removed from the carcass for visual post-mortem examination and physical palpation of the organ.

described by [25]. A thorough inspection was conducted on the mandibular, retropharyngeal, left and right bronchial, cranial and caudal mediastinal, and mesenteric lymph nodes, as well as the lungs (Plate 2), liver, and kidneys. The lungs, comprising seven lobes, were first examined externally and palpated for abnormalities. Each lobe was then sliced into 2 cm-thick sections to facilitate the detection of tuberculous lesions. Similarly, the lymph nodes were sectioned to approximately the same thickness and examined carefully for gross lesions.

From each carcass, approximately 100 grams of lung tissue were excised using sterile scissors and forceps. Samples were placed into clean, sterile, screw-capped plastic containers, and properly labeled. The samples were transported on ice to Biotechnology Laboratory of the National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI), Vom, and stored at -20°C .

Plate 2: Post-mortem examination of lungs with tubercules

2.10 Tissue Homogenization

Using sterile forceps and blades, 100 g each of the collected tissues were transferred into a 2ml Eppendorf tube. One 5-mm steel bead was added to each tube, along with 500 μl of phosphate buffer saline (PBS) and then homogenized in a Tissue Lyser III (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). The homogenate was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 2 min and the supernatant was decanted into clean micro centrifuge tubes that were properly labeled. These were stored at -20°C until needed for DNA extraction.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the molecular analysis of lung tissue samples

2.11 Molecular isolation and PCR analysis

DNA extraction was performed using the ExtractME® Kit DNA extraction kit, following the manufacturer's protocol. Samples previously stored at -20°C were thawed at room temperature. The homogenates were inactivated using proteinase K enzyme and lysis buffer in the BSL3 laboratory of the NVRI, Vom. The PCR reaction contained $12.5\mu\text{l}$ of 2X master mix, $1.0\mu\text{l}$ ($10\text{pmol}/\mu\text{l}$) each of primer (forward and reverse), $7.5\mu\text{l}$ of Nuclease-free water, and $3\mu\text{l}$ of template DNA, making a final volume of $25\mu\text{l}$. Amplification was initiated by initial denaturation at 94°C for 5 minutes and this was followed by 35 cycles of 94°C for 1 minute, 68°C for 1 minute, and 72°C for 1 minute. This was followed by incubation for a final extension at 72°C for 10 minutes. The PCR was carried out in a

Thermal cycler (Applied Biosystems GeneAmp PCR System 9700). PCR products were fractionated electrophoretically in 2% agarose gel stained in ethidium bromide in 1x TBE buffer, pH 8.3 at 90 volts for 1 hour 30 minutes, and visualized under UV light (as shown in Plates 3 and 4). The size of the amplicons was determined by comparison with a 50bp DNA ladder. Established primers which amplified a fragment of 123 base pairs (bp) of the conserved MTB complex sequence, IS6110 TB1 (5'-CCTGCGAGCGTAGGCGTCGG-3' and TB2 5'-CTCGTCCAGCGCCGCTTCGG-3'), [26] and with specific primers for *M. bovis*, which amplified a fragment of 186 bp of *pncA* gene (5'-ATGCGGGCGTTGATCATCGTC-3' and 5'-CGGTGTGCCGAGAAGCCG-3') [27] were used in this study.

Plate 3. Detection of MTB using polymerase chain reaction technique.

M= Molecular base ladder (50bp).

Samples=84-96.

Amplified fragment of 123 base pairs (bp) of the conserved MTB complex sequence

Plate 4. Detection of *M. bovis* using polymerase chain reaction technique.

Amplified fragment of 186 bp of *pncA* gene.

M= Molecular base ladder (50bp),

Samples= 1-10 with Positive= +ve and Negative control= -ve

2.12 Questionnaire

A structured questionnaire using simple random sampling technique was administered to 150 subjects including butchers, traders, and animal health personnel to collect data on associated risk factors for bovine tuberculosis. The questionnaire was designed with different parts to collect data on sociodemographic factors of the respondents, their contacts with animals, and their knowledge about tuberculosis. Before the commencement of the study, the questionnaire was first pilot tested in an abattoir in Jos, which was not sampled for the study so as to check the validity and reliability of the questionnaire items.

2.13 Ethical Considerations

The study involved the use of animals destined for slaughter; therefore, ethical clearance was not required to carry out the study because we were not directly involved in the live handling of the live animals or the slaughter process itself. Only post-mortem lung samples were used.

3.0 Data Analysis

The data from the study was entered into Excel for cleaning and thereafter imported into STATA version 14.0 for statistical analysis. The chi-square test was used to determine if there was a significant difference between the prevalence of MTB complex and *M. bovis* infection as well as if there was a significant difference in the responses by respondents to the different questions raised. Results were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2: Prevalence of MTB complex in sampled cattle

Variable	Level	No. examined	No. infected	Percentage infected	p value
Sex	Female	85	43	69.35	0.713
	Male	35	19	30.65	
Location	Plateau	100	48	48.0	0.192
	Taraba	9	6	66.67	
	Borno	11	8	72.73	

Results on the detection of *M. bovis* in the collected tissue samples (Table 3) revealed that 15.29% (13/85) females were infected compared to the 20% (7/35) infection recorded in males. However, this was not significant ($p > 0.05$). Across location,

4.0 Result

4.1 Proportion of cattle infected with MTB complex and *M. bovis*

Table 1 shows the proportion of cattle infected with MTB complex and *M. bovis*. Overall, 62 (51.67%) of the samples were positive for MTB complex, out of which 20 (16.67%), were positive for *M. bovis*. The lungs were identified as the primary organs affected by tuberculous lesions; however, in our study the lungs appeared apparently healthy (Plate 2).

Table 1: Proportion of samples infected with MTB complex and *M. bovis* (n=120)

Pathogen	No. infected	% infected
MTB complex	62	51.67
<i>M. bovis</i>	20	16.67

The prevalence of MTB complex in the studied cattle is contained in Table 2. Infection was higher in the females (69.35%, 43/85) compared to the males (30.65%, 19/35) however this was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Geographically, higher prevalence of MBT complex were recorded in Borno (72.73%, 8/11) and Taraba (66.67, 6/9) states compared to Plateau state (48.0, 48/100). However, the observed difference was also not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Borno and Taraba states recorded 36.36% (4/11) and 22.22% (2/9) infection respectively, against the 14% (14/100) prevalence recorded in Plateau State. However, the observed difference was also not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3: Prevalence of *M. bovis* in sampled cattle

Variable	Level	No. examined	No. infected	Percentage infected	p value
Sex	Female	85	13	15.29	0.530
	Male	35	7	20.0	
Location	Plateau	100	14	14.0	0.151
	Taraba	9	2	22.22	
	Borno	11	4	36.36	

4.2 Demographic information of the respondents

Table 4 contains the demographic characteristics of respondents interviewed. 98% of the respondents

were male with only 2% as females. Most of the respondents were aged 41-50 years old (38%) and 31-40% (29%) and have acquired secondary education (40%) ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4: Demographic information of the respondents

Category	Response	Frequency	Percent	P value
Gender	Male	98	98	<0.001
	Female	2	2	
Age	20-30	18	18	<0.001
	31-40	29	29	
	41-50	38	38	
	51-60	14	14	
	61- above	1	1	
Level of Education	None	8	8	<0.001
	Primary	25	25	
	Secondary	40	40	
	Tertiary	25	25	
	Qu'ranic	2	2	

4.3 Information on respondents' contact with animals

Table 5 contains information on respondents' contact with animals. Most of the respondents in the study reported contacts with between 1-10 (34%) and 11-20 (33%) animals ($p < 0.05$). Although a slightly higher number (54%) of the respondents

keep animals, this did not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$) from those who did not (46%). The commonest animals kept were cattle and goat (44%) and cattle and sheep (24%) ($p < 0.05$). However, there was no distinction between those who care for the animals themselves (50%) and those that did not (50%).

Table 5:Information on respondents' contact with animals

Category	Response	Frequency	Percent	P value
Number of animals you come in contact with daily	1-10	34	34	<0.001
	11-20	33	33	
	21-30	18	18	
	31-40	6	6	
	41-50	7	7	
	51-60	1	1	
	>60	1	1	
Do you own/keep animals?	Yes	54	54	0.424
	No	46	46	
If yes what are the characteristics of the herd?	cattle only	9	17	0.008
	cattle with sheep	13	24	
	cattle with goats	24	44	
	cattle with sheep and goats	8	15	
Do you take care of them yourself?	Yes	27	50	
	No	27	50	

4.4 Respondents Knowledge about Tuberculosis

On knowledge of respondents about tuberculosis (Table 6), a significantly ($p < 0.05$) high number of the population (98%) have heard about tuberculosis. With health workers (24%) and radio (22%) as the most common sources of information. Majority of the respondents (79%) know about the major clinical signs and symptoms of TB and are aware that TB is also a human disease (94%), which could be contracted from animals (79%) ($p < 0.05$). Ninety-three percent (93%) of the respondents are familiar with the mode of transmission of the disease, noting the common means of transmission as through the air (64%) when a person with TB coughs or sneezes. Furthermore, 73% of the

respondents said they know that tuberculosis can be controlled by Vaccination in infancy ($p < 0.05$). However, as to whether TB Vaccine exists for adults, there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between those who are aware of it (48%) or not (52%), even though they all noted that anyone (100%) can be infected with TB.

Most respondents (92%) in this study noted that they call a Vet if they notice signs of TB in their animals, and that TB infection can be cured (93%) through treatments using drugs at the hospital (64%) ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, 70% of the respondents also stated that covering the mouth and nose when coughing or sneezing (70%) is a way of preventing TB infection ($p < 0.05$).

Table 6: Knowledge about Tuberculosis

Category	Response	Frequency	Percent	P value
Heard about tuberculosis (tarin fuka)?	Yes	98	98	<0.001
	No	2	2	
Where did you first learn about tuberculosis?	Newspapers and magazine	2	2	0.032
	Radio	22	22	
	Health workers	24	24	
	Family	5	5	
	Friends	18	18	
	Neighbors	5	5	
	Teachers	15	15	
	Market	2	2	
	Hospital	5	5	
	Seminar	2	2	
	Do you know about some major clinical signs/symptoms?	Yes	79	
No		21	21	
Have you heard of tuberculosis as a human disease?	Yes	94	94	<0.001
	No	6	6	
Do you know that humans can get the diseases from animals?	Yes	79	79	<0.001
	No	21	21	
Do you know the mode of transmission to humans?	Yes	73	73	<0.001
	No	27	27	
How do you think a person can get TB?	Through handshakes	9	9	<0.001
	Through the air when a person with TB coughs or sneezes	64	64	
	Through eating from the same plate	11	11	

	Through touching items in public places (doorknobs, faucets, etc)	6	6	
	Do not know	3	3	
	All the above	7	7	
Do you know that tuberculosis can be controlled by Vaccination in infancy?	Yes	73	73	<0.001
	No	27	27	
TB Vaccine in adults does not exist?	Yes	48	48	0.689
	No	52	52	
Who can be infected with TB?	Anybody	100	100	
What do you do when you notice your cattle has signs of TB?	Call a vet	92	92	<0.001
	Slaughter	6	6	
	Throwaway	1	1	
	Sell	1	1	
Can TB be cured?	Yes	93	93	<0.001
	No	7	7	
How can someone with TB be cured?	Herbal remedies	18	18	<0.001
	Praying	7	7	
	Do not know Others	11	11	
	Drugs/treatment/hosp.	64	64	
How can a person prevent getting TB?	Avoid shaking of hands	9	9	<0.001
	Covering mouth and nose when coughing or sneezing	70	70	

Avoid sharing plates	10	10
Through good nutrition	5	5
By praying	5	5
Do not know	1	1

5.0 Discussion

This study found an overall *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC) prevalence of 52% with higher infection recorded in female animals and Borno followed by Taraba States recording the highest infection. This prevalence is high compared to the 33.3 % reported by Obialigwe et al. [28] in Taraba state. Earlier, Okeke et al. [29] in their study, reported a prevalence of 16.7% in Jos. However, the current finding is similar to the 50% prevalence reported by [30] in their study in Borno State. Contrary to our finding, where only 17% of tissue samples tested were positive for *M. bovis*, [30] reported a prevalence of 65.4%. However, this result is still high and could be linked to insufficient control measures in livestock management, and poor diagnostic surveillance in the abattoirs.

Although higher record of MTB complex was found in the female cattle, on the contrary, higher record of *M. bovis* was encountered in the males although, there was no significant difference in the observed infection in both cases ($p > 0.05$). It is likely that the high record of MTB complex in female animals could be due to the management practices, where herd owners tend to retain more females due to their reproductive value which may increase their level of exposure to the pathogen. However, previous works [32] have reported that cows (especially those experiencing pregnancy, parturition, and lactation) tend to show higher bTB prevalence compared to males. The stress and immune demands of reproduction were suggested as contributing factors. Furthermore, the high prevalence of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex detected in apparently normal lungs, suggests a widespread subclinical or latent infections that may evade detection during routine inspection. This finding raises serious public health concerns,

especially within endemic regions, as such undetected reservoirs could perpetuate the transmission of tuberculosis (TB), particularly in high-risk settings such as abattoirs and among immunocompromised individuals. In addition, this finding highlights the limitations of visual inspection alone for detecting bovine TB and the need for improved ante- and post-mortem diagnostic tools, such as PCR, or interferon-gamma assays, especially in slaughterhouse settings.

In the current study, there was no significant difference in the observed prevalence of both MTB complex and *M. bovis* across location although higher prevalence was observed in Borno and Taraba states compared to Plateau state, suggesting that bovine tuberculosis may be prevalent in all parts of Nigeria [32]. Management practices such as migration of nomadic herds across the country in search of greener pasture during the dry and the rainy seasons and the presence and buildup of *Mycobacterium* infections in the environment could be some of the reasons for the widespread distribution of bovine tuberculosis in the country [33].

Apart from the reported cases of bovine tuberculosis, there has been reported cases of zoonotic transmission of *Mycobacterium bovis* from cattle to humans [34].

Markets and abattoirs handle a high volume of animals daily, including infected and non-infected ones, and it is observed that slaughtering and processing are typically carried out without the use of protective clothing, and during the handling of carcasses, food and drinks are often consumed with blood-stained hands, posing a significant risk of zoonotic transmission to butchers and their families. Aerosol transmission of bovine tuberculosis remains a concern for meat industry and slaughterhouse workers, especially in regions where

the disease is still prevalent in livestock [35]. Of concern in this study was the observed smuggling of tuberculous organs out of the abattoir, which were often sold to the public or kept for regular customers, such as restaurant or beer parlour operators which may increase the risk if zoonotic transmission in the public thus, posing severe threat to public health.

The results highlight a generally high awareness of tuberculosis (TB) among the respondents, particularly within a predominantly male, middle-aged population with a secondary education background. The significant skew in gender (98% male) likely reflects occupational demographics in rural livestock-keeping or agricultural communities, as seen in previous studies where men often engage more directly with animal care and trade [36,37]. The age distribution, with most respondents between 31–50 years old, aligns with the economically active and livestock-handling age group, potentially increasing their exposure risk to zoonotic infections.

Regarding animal contact, most respondents reported frequent interaction with animals, particularly cattle, goats, and sheep, consistent with findings in pastoralist communities where such animals serve economic and nutritional functions [38]. Although animal ownership was high (54%), it is noteworthy that there was no significant difference in disease knowledge between those who owned animals and those who did not, suggesting community-wide awareness beyond direct exposure.

Knowledge about TB was commendably high. A vast majority (98%) had heard about TB, with health workers and radio identified as the main information sources, echoing studies that underscore the importance of local media and health campaigns in disease awareness [39, 40]. The respondents demonstrated good understanding of TB symptoms (79%) and modes of transmission (93%), especially airborne spread through coughing and sneezing (64%). This is consistent with the earlier work by [41] in Kano where respondents also showed a high level of awareness on the environmental determinants of TB. Although, they suggested enhanced public health messaging to bridge knowledge gaps owing to discrepancies in perceptions regarding hygiene, overcrowding, and waste management suggest a need for. Awareness of zoonotic transmission of bovine tuberculosis was

also significant (79%), indicating a strong recognition of animal-human disease transmission pathways, a critical point for One Health approaches [42]. Most respondents knew TB could be prevented through vaccination during infancy (73%), although there was ambiguity regarding adult vaccination, with no significant difference between those who were aware and those who were not. This knowledge gap indicates the need for targeted education on adult TB prevention.

Encouragingly, nearly all respondents acknowledged that TB is curable (93%) and treatable at hospitals (64%) and emphasized the importance of preventive measures like respiratory hygiene (70%). These findings reflect a population that is not only aware but also willing to take action, such as contacting a veterinarian for sick animals (92%), aligning with similar studies advocating community engagement in zoonotic TB control [43].

6.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, the study reveals a high prevalence of *Mycobacterium bovis* in cattle sampled from Borno and Taraba, as compared to Plateau state, and substantial exposure risk among abattoir workers. The unexpectedly high prevalence of MTBC (52%), particularly *M. bovis* (17%), in asymptomatic lungs and among females suggests a potentially underappreciated public health threat. These findings underscore the urgent need to strengthen TB control policies, routine screening enhancements, and implement community-based awareness programs targeting both zoonotic and human TB transmission. Despite these risks, the community demonstrated commendable awareness of tuberculosis, its symptoms, transmission, and prevention, reflecting the effectiveness of public health outreach through health workers and local media. However, gaps in knowledge regarding adult vaccination and continued risky practices at slaughter points underscore the urgent need for targeted education and stronger enforcement of bio safety protocols to curb zoonotic transmission.

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Conflict of interest

The authors of this article declare no competing interests concerning its publication.

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